

Original Research Article

Levels of stress regarding clinical performance and academic excellence among first year B.Sc. nursing students in St. Xavier's Catholic College of Nursing, Chunkankadai

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Abstract

A descriptive study to assess the level of stress regarding academic excellence and clinical performance of first year B.Sc. nursing students in St. Xavier's Catholic College of Nursing, Chunkankadai.

Introduction:

Nursing education can be very stressful, students experience increased tension due to its demanding paper work and skill performance nursing education is demanding. Learning to cope with stress is a useful skill for a nursing career and life ahead.

Objectives:

- To assess the levels of stress regarding clinical performance among students.
- To assess the levels of stress regarding academic excellence among students.
- To relate level of stress regarding academic excellence and clinical performance among students.
- To relate academic excellence and demographic variables.
- To relate clinical performance and demographic variables.

Major Findings:

The level of stress of the entire sample revealed 43.3% had mild level of stress. 46.67% had moderate level of stress and 10% had severe level of stress regarding clinical performance. The level of stress of the entire sample revealed 6.67% had mild level of stress, 70% had moderate level of stress and 23.33% had severe level of stress regarding academic excellence. Positive correlation was found between level of stress regarding academic excellence and level of stress regarding clinical performance. Hence it was interpreted that when level of stress regarding academic excellence increases, level of stress regarding clinical performance will be increased and also it is significant.

Keywords: Stress, Clinical Performance, Academic Excellence

INTRODUCTION

From the large number of stresses faced by adolescents and young adults, academic stress emerges as a significant mental health problem in recent years. It has been estimated that 10% to 30% students experience academic related stress that affects their academic performance. Information load, high expectation, academic burden or pressure, unrealistic ambitions, limited opportunities, high competitiveness are some of the sources of stress which create tension, fear, and anxiety. If the nurse can take care of herself alone, she will be able to take care of her clients. Certain related studies conducted by others include depression, stress, emotional support and self-esteem among nursing students by Ratchneewan Ross in 2005. One news report shown that most college students are under high levels of stress. The nursing students have to face additional pressures. Their academic year is longer and they have to contend with the clinical demands, such as working with sick and dying patients. Nursing students also have to deal with the tensions inherent in the transient, but intense relationships with patients and colleagues that characterize much of the health care. Most nursing students are female and many have dependents and other commitments that must be managed alongside their training.

Research methods or Methodology:**Research approach:** Quantitative research approach**Research Design:** Descriptive research design**Setting:** St. Xavier's Catholic College of Nursing, Chunkankadai, an esteemed institution affiliated to Dr. M.G.R. Medical University, Guindy, Chennai.**Population:** The target population is first year B.Sc. nursing students**Sample size:** 30**Sampling method:** Convenient sampling technique**Research Tool:** Part A-Demographic profile of the sample such as age, sex, religion, monthly income, type of residence, type of house and type of syllabus previously studied.

Part B-Stress Scale was used to assess the level of stress among first year B. Sc. Nursing students.

DISCUSSION

The level of stress of the entire sample revealed 43.3% had mild level of stress. 46.67% had moderate level of stress and 10% had severe level of stress regarding clinical performance. The level of stress of the entire sample revealed 6.67% had mild level of stress, 70% had moderate level of stress and 23.33% had severe level of stress regarding academic excellence. Positive correlation was found between level of stress regarding academic excellence and level of stress regarding clinical performance. Hence it was interpreted that when level of stress regarding academic excellence increases, level of stress regarding clinical performance will be increased and also it is significant. There was no significant association between level of stress regarding academic excellence and clinical performance with the selected demographic variables of age, sex, religion, type of house, type of residence and syllabus previously studied. This study may help to draw the attention of nurses to have good control over stress in various areas of nursing like administration, education, practice and research.

In order to develop good control over stress nurse should have personal and professional knowledge and make arrangements to conduct in-service education programme. The nurse administrator should educate the nurses about coping strategies to overcome the stress. The nurse administrator should take up leadership roles in training and providing health education programme to nursing personnel so that these personnel take up active role in educating the nurses for providing information about variety of coping strategies that can be used by student nurses to overcome the stress.

The student nurses from school of nursing and college of nursing should be encouraged to attend specialized courses, conferences, workshops and seminars regarding coping strategies for reduction of stress. Efforts should be made to improve and expand nursing curriculum to include student stress coping strategies, which can contribute to significant stress reduction. Nurses can conduct teaching sessions for student nurses by giving their life experience which will help them in maintaining good control over stress. The stress coping counselling imparted to the student nurses is highly beneficial for the young student nurses. The staff nurses as the professional health care worker are able to make significant contribution to promote the development of stress coping skills of student nurses. Extensive research must be conducted in this area to assess the level of stress of first year B.Sc. nursing students regarding academic excellence and clinical performance. The emerging researchers can effectively utilize this study for their research regarding the levels of stress not only among student nurses but also among nursing instructors.

This study may be replicated using a large population. A similar study can be conducted and evaluated using alternative strategies like self-instructional modules, video methods etc.

Table and Figures:**Table 1 Frequency and percentage distribution of sample according to demographic variables**

Sl. No.	Demographic variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age		
	17-18 years	-	0
	19-20 years	27	90
	21-22 years	3	10
2	Sex		
	Male	0	0
	Female	30	100
3	Monthly Income		
	< ₹5000	13	43.4
	₹5001-10,000	11	36.6
	₹10,000 and above	6	20

4	Religion		
	Hindu	8	26.6
	Christian	22	73.4
	Muslim	0	0
5	Type of residence		
	Urban	11	36.6
	Rural	19	63.4
6	Type of house		
	Thatched	5	16.6
	Tiled	10	33.4
	Terraced	15	50
7	Syllabus previously studied		
	C.B.S.E.	0	0
	I.C.S.E.	0	0
	State Board	26	86.6
	Matriculation	4	13.4

N=30

Figure 1: Percentage distribution of sample according to the age

N=30

Figure 2: Percentage distribution of sample according to the sex

N=30

Figure 3: Percentage distribution of sample according to the monthly income

N=30

Figure 4: Percentage distribution of sample according to the religion

N=30

Figure 5: Percentage distribution of sample according to the type of residence

N=30

Figure 6: Percentage distribution of sample according to the type of house

N=30

Figure 7: Percentage distribution of sample according to the syllabus previously studied

Table – 2

Frequency and distribution of level of stress regarding academic excellence among first year B.Sc. Nursing students of St. Xavier’s Catholic College of Nursing, Chunkankadai.

Sl.No.	Level of stress regarding academic excellence	Frequency	Percentage
1	Mild level of stress	2	6.67%
2	Moderate level of stress	21	70%
3	Severe level of stress	7	23.33%

N=30

Figure 8: Percentage distribution of level of stress regarding academic excellence

Table – 3

Frequency and distribution of level of stress regarding clinical performance among first year B.Sc. Nursing students of St. Xavier’s Catholic College of Nursing, Chunkankadai.

Sl.No.	Level of stress regarding clinical performance	Frequency	Percentage
1	Mild level of stress	13	43.33%
2	Moderate level of stress	14	46.67%
3	Severe level of stress	3	10%

Figure 9: Percentage distribution of level of stress regarding clinical performance

Table-4

Relationship between the level of stress regarding academic excellence and clinical performance among first year B.Sc. nursing students in St. Xavier’s Catholic College of Nursing, Chunkankadai.

Sl.No.	Variable	Coefficient	Result
	Academic excellence	r=+1	Positive Correlation
2.	Clinical performance		

Table-5

Association between level of stress and clinical performance among first year B.Sc. nursing students with selected demographic variables of age, sex, religion, monthly income, type of house, type of syllabus previously studied.

N=30

Sl.no.	Demographic variables	Chi-square Value	df value	Table value
1	Age	1.43	4	9.49 (NS)
2	Sex	0	2	5.99 (NS)
3	Income	2.23	4	9.49 (NS)
4	Religion	4.67	4	9.49 (NS)
5	Type of house	4.48	4	9.49 (NS)
6	Type of residence	5.02	2	5.99 (NS)
7	Syllabus previously studied	30.66	6	12.59 (NS)

S: Significant**NS: Not Significant****Table – 6**

Association between level of stress and academic excellence among first year B.Sc. nursing students with selected demographic variables of age, sex, religion, monthly income, type of house, type of syllabus, and type of previously studied syllabus.

N=30

Sl.no.	Demographic variables	Chi-square value	df value	Table value
1	Age	1.92	4	9.49 (NS)
2	Sex	0	2	5.99 (NS)
3	Income	2.28	4	9.49 (NS)
4	Religion	6.25	4	9.49 (NS)
5	Type of house	2.69	4	9.49 (NS)
6	Type of residence	0.06	2	5.99 (NS)
7	Syllabus previously studied	2.26	6	12.59 (NS)

S: Significant**NS: Not Significant**

CONCLUSION

43.3% had mild level of stress, 46.67% had moderate level of stress and 10% had severe level of stress regarding clinical performance. 6.67% had mild level of stress, 70% had moderate level of stress and 23.3% had severe level of stress regarding academic excellence. It was found that when level of stress regarding academic excellence increases, level of stress regarding clinical performance was increased. There was no significant association between level of stress regarding academic excellence and clinical performance with the selected demographic variables of age, sex, religion, type of house, type of residence and syllabus previously studied.

REFERENCES

1. Jacob A. Stress and its Management. Psychology for graduate Nurses, First Edition, Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers. Page No. 74-81
2. Townsend C.M. The concept of stress adaptation. Psychiatric (Mental) Health Nursing, Fifth Edition. Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers 2007. Page No:4-8
3. Davis E.M. Stress management is key during nursing school. The student voice, 2004;4:2-3. Available from <http://onsopcontent.ons.org/publications/1/Nov/041/article5.html>
4. Honor N. Journals of Advanced Nursing Programme.2005;50:93-100
5. Jones M.C., Johnston. Stress and coping in First Year Student Nurses. Journal of Advanced Nursing Distress 1997; 8:10-12. Available from http://www.sdps.worc.ac.uk/subjects_and_challengesnursing_anxiety.html